

Online Appendix. Rubric for Evaluating Indicators of Student Commitment to Computer-Supported Collaboration

Variable	Does not meet expectations (0)	Meets expectations (1)	Exceeds expectations (2)
A: Cooperative goal setting			
A1. There is a clear process for goal setting in the team			
A2. The process is perceived to be fair			
A3. There was a discussion of individual motivations before deciding on the team goal and the allocation of subgoals to team members.			
A4. The team is able solve disputes related to choosing goals			
B: Goal tracking and achievement			
B1. Team members know what goals are being worked on			
B2. Team members can request support from each other			
B3. There is a proactive stance on goal tracking			
B4. There is a process to track and re-allocate workload in case of issues			
C: Effective communication			
C1. Team has default communication channels			
C2. Team members know how to reach all other members in a timely manner			
C3. Communication is efficient and supports team activities			
C4. Communicating status and issues has no single point of failure (e.g. mail forwards and updates by one team member)			
D: Level of collaboration			
D1. Team members work towards shared goals			
D2. Team members also work cooperatively towards goals			
D3. Team recognizes learning goals as valid goals			
D4. Team members collaborate (support each other in achieving learning goals)			

The rubric consists of four categories marked from A to D. Observations are marked by checking the box for each item. The next pages contain recommended expectations for each variable.

Recommended definitions of “meets expectations” for each variable.

Variable	Expectations
A: Cooperative goal setting	
A1. There is a clear process for goal setting in the team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team members know how to affect the group goals. • There was a consideration of how individual goals align with the team goal and the course goals. • All team members knew at the start what is the team goal and what were the individual goals
A2. The process is perceived to be fair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each team member felt that his or her opinions were taken into account when deciding the goal. • If a team member was not able to impact the team goal, everyone understood why it was not possible to choose a proposed goal. • If imbalances in work allocation arose during teamwork, the team was able to solve the issues or redistribute work in a manner that was perceived as fair to everyone.
A3. There was a discussion of individual motivations before deciding on the team goal and the allocation of subgoals to team members.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a discussion of each team member’s motivations. • Each member’s learning goals, competencies and preferences were discussed when deciding on team goal and allocation of subgoals to each team member.
A4. The team is able solve disputes related to choosing goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The team was able to handle disagreements that arose during goal decision to everyone’s satisfaction. • Team members were able to raise objections and disagreements without fearing overly negative comments from a single member.
B: Goal tracking and achievement	
B1. Team members know what goals are being worked on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project, all team members knew what other team members were doing.
B2. Team members can request support from each other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was possible to ask for mutual help or request work to be reallocated if an individual goal was found to be too challenging.
B3. There is a proactive stance on goal tracking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team members actively shared their status, either in a shared communication channel or automatically with an online system (i.e. issue tracker, project management tool or a source code repository).
B4. There is a process to track and re-allocate workload in case of issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a process or a shared understanding of how to re-allocate or share workload in the team. • Each member reported their status often enough that no single section of project was on the verge of failing without other team members knowing about it. • No one member of the team was overloaded with a disproportionate workload.

C: Effective communication	
C1. Team has default communication channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The team has a default online communication channel and a method to communicate to all members at the same time or individually.
C2. Team members know how to reach all other members in a timely manner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members know how to reach all other team members in a manner that enables continuous teamwork and problem solving. The delay in reaching other team members has not caused frustrations in a majority of the team.
C3. Communication is efficient and supports team activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members communicated with each other, especially in topics related to group processing, mutual support, promotive interaction or collaborative learning. Team members found the chosen communication platform to be useful and to support team activities.
C4. Communicating status and issues has no single point of failure (e.g. mail forwards and updates by one team member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is an online platform or other method of sharing status so that team status can be communicated without having to ask a single person. The communication within a team functions without the assistance of a “team secretary.”
D: Level of collaboration	
D1. Team members work towards shared goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members all work together to accomplish the same course goal.
D2. Team members also work cooperatively towards goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members have divided the course goal into subgoals Team members work simultaneously to accomplish the subgoals. Team members might still have different <i>learning</i> goals.
D3. Team recognizes learning goals as valid goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members acknowledge that they are also learning as a team. It is clear for all team members what are the learning goals of the course
D4. Team members collaborate (support each other in achieving learning goals)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members collaborate, i.e. work <i>together</i> on goals and not only individually on subgoals. Team members learn collaboratively, i.e. support each other in learning new things related to the course or support less experienced team members in getting started. Team members understand the big picture and help each other in achieving all individual, team and learning goals.

Regarding the exceeds expectations category: If all “meets expectations” criteria have been achieved and then some requirements of the category have been achieved exceptionally well or clearly exceeded, then the category can be marked as “exceeds expectations.”

There are several goals in a course and team environment mentioned in the rubric. They are defined as follows:

- Individual goal: Something that an individual team member has been assigned to do, or has decided to do.
- Team goal: A goal that has been negotiated between team members and has been accepted as a goal for the team.
- Course goal: All tasks that students or student teams should accomplish during a course.
- Learning goal: The new subjects that the students should learn during the course, as defined by the curriculum.
- Valid goal: A goal that an individual or a team has acknowledged as a goal that should be pursued.

When citing the rubric, please use the following information:

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Presenting the rubric design process and relating it to literature on collaboration

This metric and its evaluation rubric are based on a grounded theory study on three collaborative courses and existing literature. The research has been published in the ITiCSE 2017 conference. Please see the rubric website at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.546087> for a link to the conference publication and for more related material. The following sections offer a short review of the metric design process, rationale for rubric categories and relation to existing literature.

1. A Metric for Measuring Indicators of Student Commitment to Computer-Supported Collaboration

Grounded Theory analysis enables the describing of phenomena, describing actor strategies and identifying factors affecting those strategies, but at its core, it is a qualitative data analysis method and does not allow building metrics. Because of this, we chose a mixed method approach, where we identify and describe the phenomena using the first two steps of the Strauss-Corbin version of Grounded Theory [7]. After the initial analysis, we build an evaluation rubric using the most important codes identified in the analysis. This allows building an evaluation metric for comparing different collaboration situations, enables more lightweight analysis in future case studies, and allows comparison of team outcomes between case studies. In the next subsection, we describe four variables, built on the Grounded Theory categories that are related to team commitment according to our research, and how these individual indicators relate to commitment.

1.1 Defining indicators, the metric and the evaluation rubric

The first indicator is *cooperative goal setting processes*, which is crucial in longer-term teamwork. It describes both the team's decision of what the overall goals are, and how the subgoals based on these goals are divided among the team members. It is crucial to motivation that the students perceive this process to be fair and that they feel that they have been able to affect the direction of teamwork. This furthers individual ownership of team goals, because it allows the team members to feel that they have participated in setting the goals. A process that allows the students to solve disputes also furthers individual commitment to goals.

The second indicator is *goal tracking and achievement*, and it is related to effective communications. It measures how well the team follows who has achieved their goals and whether the team balances workloads. Goal tracking allows the individuals to relate their individual progress to shared team progress and see how their efforts promote the advancement of the shared, overall goal.

The third indicator is *effective communication*, which is another important aspect for group cohesion. Communication is not only important for organizing teamwork, but also maintaining social cohesion. Teams are always social units to some extent and if individuals feel that other team members are passive, there is a possibility that they feel being passive is acceptable for them as well. This means student teams with slow or erratic communication can start to drift apart in both social cohesion and goal direction. Effective communication also promotes group processing and positive social interactions.

The fourth indicator is the *level of collaboration*. Collaboration in this context means mutual support towards shared learning goals instead of just cooperating to achieve individual student goals. It is another important aspect of teamwork and mutual support, and collaboration is what separates a group of individuals from a learning, working team. Good collaboration and mutual support can also increase individual motivation.

Using these indicators and the categories found in the grounded theory analysis, we defined a rubric for evaluating the level of each indicator. The rubric variables are presented in the Table 1. Each variable is evaluated using the following scale: Does not meet expectations (0), meets expectations (1) and exceeds expectations (2). This means that the minimum amount of points awarded from each category (marked with an alphabet and in bold text in the table) is zero and maximum eight. Maximum amount of points awarded from the metric is 32. The evaluation rubric is printed out in full at the start of the Online Appendix.

Table 1. A list of variables used in the rubric for evaluating indicators of student commitment, sorted by indicators

A: Cooperative goal setting processes	B: Goal tracking and achievement	C: Effective communication	D: Level of collaboration
1. There is a clear process for goal setting 2. The process is perceived to be fair 3. There was a discussion of individual motivations before goal decision and allocation 4. Ability to solve disputes	1. Team members know what goals are being worked on 2. Team members can request support from each other 3. Proactive stance on goal tracking 4. Process to track and re-allocate workload in case of issues	1. Team has default communication channels 2. Team members know how to reach all other members in a timely manner 3. Communication is efficient and supports team activities 4. Communicating status and issues has no single point of failure	1. Team members work towards shared goals 2. Team members work cooperatively towards goals 3. Team recognizes learning goals as valid goals 4. Team members collaborate (support others in achieving learning goals)

1.2 Relating the categories to existing literature

Serrano-Camara et al. [6] discuss the several types of motivation in learning from intrinsic motivations of Deci & Ryan's self-determination theory [2] to external motivation like rewards and regulation, and state that fostering intrinsic motivation is essential in collaborative learning environments. In their study and their review of the literature, they establish a link between intrinsic motivation and positive consequences. When comparing their research [6], theories on motivation [1, 2] and the presented metric, similarities can be found between aspects of teamwork in the metric and factors that promote intrinsic motivation, group processing and team regulation.

Cooperative goal setting processes (A) are related to the intrinsic motivation of autonomy. Regular group processing, clear goals, establishing working norms and mutual trust has also been shown to impact student satisfaction and learning processes [4, 5].

Goal tracking and achievement (B) are related to both intrinsic motivation of competence and successful team regulation. Additionally, change tracking and goal management have been found to be beneficial to team collaboration [5, 8].

Effective communication (C) is also connected to successful team regulation and the intrinsic motivation of relatedness. Additionally, group cohesion, which is promoted by effective communication (C), has been found to be an important part of team-based learning [5, 8, 9].

The level of collaboration (D) is more complex to relate as a category, because it is an overall indicator of a complex phenomenon. However, according to the study by Boekaerts & Minnaert [1], successful collaboration relates to competence level, autonomy and social relatedness. Essentially good collaboration requires mutual support towards learning goals and communication in the form of promotive interaction, positive interdependence and group processing [3, 4].

1.3 Discussion on the metric

In this study, we identified several factors that affect commitment to team goals and collaboration, and present a metric for measuring them. In the process of creating the metric, we found several identifiers that are connected to commitment in addition to initial motivation. These are goal setting processes, goal tracking, effective communication and level of collaboration. They do not have direct causality with individual commitment, but are indirect indicators of it. For example, having a successful cooperative goal setting process requires a certain level of organization and effort from the team.

The presented metric extends measuring student commitment beyond direct inquiry about student motivation. It does so by using several indicators of commitment that were detected in a qualitative study. The metric uses an observation-based approach and qualitative observations as a data source. The metric can be used to find issues in the functioning of a single team or used as an average measure to evaluate different versions of course arrangements.

The main limitation of the metric is that it requires a qualified observer and a qualitative analysis of the observed process. While the metric and the indicators can be expressed concisely, filling the rubric requires effort. The second limitation is the scope of testing. While the metric is based on a wide study of three courses from two universities, it still requires further testing and comparisons to existing metrics for validation. This testing and evaluation of how widely applicable the indicators are, is a critical direction for future research.

References

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